

Protocol: Legumes as a substitute for red and processed meat, poultry, or fish, and the association with hepatobiliary blood biomarker levels in a large cohort.

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Study information

Legumes as a substitute for red and processed meat, poultry, or fish, and the association with hepatobiliary blood biomarker levels in a large cohort.

Description

Consuming legumes instead of animal-based proteins has previously been associated with favorable hepatobiliary health. However, the underlying mechanisms driving these associations are still poorly understood in humans. Therefore, this study

investigated the association between substituting legumes for meats, poultry, and fish and changes in hepatobiliary biomarker levels during a five-year follow-up period, to elucidate some of the proposed underlying pathways linking legume consumption to lower risk of liver diseases.

This research will use the UK Biobank Resource under Application Number 81520.

Objectives and hypotheses

Background

Non-communicable diseases of the liver and gallbladder pose a significant global health burden (1,2) and are closely linked to the lipid metabolism in the liver (1,2). Alterations of the lipid metabolism may therefore impact the development of hepatobiliary diseases. Diet is a modifiable risk factor related to the lipid metabolism and research has shown that consuming plant-emphasizing diets have beneficial impacts on the lipid metabolism compared to omnivorous diets (3,4). Plant-emphasizing diets promoting legume consumption instead of animal-based foods has similarly shown beneficial in relation to other major non-communicable diseases closely related to hepatobiliary health, such as cardiovascular diseases, dyslipidemia, metabolic syndrome, etc. (5–9). Legumes are low in saturated fat and rich in dietary fibre and bioactive compounds like polyphenols and peptides, which may impact hepatobiliary metabolism (10–14). They appear to reduce fat deposition in the liver while simultaneously increasing cholesterol synthesis and biliary cholesterol secretion, which may have implications for the risk of hepatobiliary disease and related comorbidities (14–20). However, the mechanisms linking legume consumption to hepatobiliary health in humans remains understudied (21). Despite well-established associations between hepatobiliary blood biomarkers and hepatobiliary health, the pathways linking legume consumption to these pathways are understudied in humans (22,21). Therefore, this project aimed to investigate the association between substituting red and processed meat, poultry, or fish with legumes and changes in hepatobiliary biomarker concentrations over time.

Hypothesis

- Replacing red and processed meat or poultry with legumes is associated with lower follow-up levels of hepatobiliary biomarkers apart from HDL-cholesterol which will increase when replacing meats or poultry with legumes.
- Replacing fish with legumes is not associated with differences in follow-up levels of hepatobiliary biomarkers.

Design plan

Study type

Observational Study. Data is collected from study subjects that are not randomly assigned to a treatment. This includes surveys, natural experiments, and regression discontinuity designs.

Blinding

No blinding is involved in this study.

Study design

The UK Biobank recruited approximately 500,000 participants between 2006 and 2010. Participants were 37-73 years old at baseline. Study protocol and more information are available elsewhere (23,24). All participants gave written, informed consent before baseline, and the study was approved by the National Information Governance Board for Health and Social Care and the National Health Service North West Multicentre Research Ethics Committee (reference number 06/MRE08/65).

Sampling plan

Existing data

Registration prior to analysis of the data. As of the date of submission, the data exist and you have accessed it, though no analysis has been conducted related to the research plan (including calculation of summary statistics). A common situation for this scenario when a large dataset exists that is used for many different studies over time, or when a data set is randomly split into a sample for exploratory analyses, and the other section of data is reserved for later confirmatory data analysis.

Explanation of existing data

The UK Biobank is a large national cohort of participants in the UK, with data collected in a standardized format the sole purpose of providing a data resource for researchers to use for health research. All information about collection procedures, limitations, and sources of bias are well established and described by the UK Biobank resource.

Because of its size of data collected, it is near impossible to a priori see patterns in the data that might

influence how the analysis will be conducted, unless specifically looked for or previously published on. In this way, we feel pre-analysis bias is minimal.

Data collection procedures

Study population and setting

At baseline, participants provided detailed information on several sociodemographic, physical, lifestyle, and health-related characteristics via self-completed touch-screen questionnaires and a computer assisted personal interview (25). Professionally trained staff did physical, anthropometric, and biomedical measures following standardized procedures (23). Diet was assessed through a touchscreen questionnaire at baseline and a 24-hour dietary assessment tool designed for the UK Biobank study. The 24-hour dietary assessment tool was completed by participants up to five times and 210,965 individuals completed one or more 24-hour dietary assessments (26). Blood samples were drawn by trained personnel at baseline and five years later (2012-2013) in a subsample of approximately 20,000 participants (23).

Assessment of diet

The Oxford WebQ was designed as an internet based 24-hour dietary assessment tool for measuring diet on repeated occasions. The questionnaire is a short set of food frequency questions on commonly eaten food groups in the British population on the day before. The questionnaire aims to measure the type and quantity of food and beverages consumed in the last 24 hours. The Oxford WebQ was compared with interviewer-administered 24-hour dietary recalls and validated for macronutrients and total energy intake using recovery biomarkers and compared with a single food frequency questionnaire (27). Recently, the Oxford WebQ nutrient calculation was updated to provide more detailed information on nutrient intakes and to incorporate new dietary variables (28). Participants recruited between April 2009 and September 2010 completed the Oxford WebQ at baseline ($n=70,747$). The Oxford WebQ was not available until April 2009 and participants recruited before that date who provided a valid email address were invited to complete the four subsequent 24-hour dietary assessments online (29).

Legumes

Legume consumption will be estimated based on participants' reported diets from the self-administered online 24-hour dietary assessments, the Oxford WebQ. Consumption of legumes and pulses will

be based on total weight by food group intakes estimated from participants' responses in the Oxford WebQ. Despite the high detail level of the Oxford WebQ, a single 24-hour dietary assessment cannot capture habitual intake of legumes in a UK setting (30). Therefore, this study will include varying numbers of 24-hour dietary assessments to ensure that we capture the usual intake of legumes. Usual intake will be estimated as a daily average across available 24-hour dietary assessments.

Meat, poultry, and fish

Consumption of red and processed meats, poultry, and fish will be based on total weight by food group intakes estimated from participants' responses to the Oxford WebQs. Red and processed meat will be defined as beef, pork, lamb, and other meats including offal, and processed meat including sausages, bacon, ham, and liver paté. Poultry will be defined as poultry with or without skin, and fried poultry with batter or breadcrumbs. Fish will be defined as oily fish, white fish and tinned tuna, fried fish with batter or breadcrumbs, and shellfish.

Outcomes

Measured biomarkers relevant for hepatobiliary health included alanine aminotransferase (ALAT), aspartate aminotransferase (ASAT), gamma glutamyltransferase (GGT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), apolipoprotein-B (ApoB), low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), total cholesterol (TC), serum triglycerides (TG), fasting blood glucose (FBG), glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), C-reactive protein (CRP), serum creatinine (sCr), sex-hormone binding glycoprotein (SHBG), and total bilirubin. Multiple biomarker levels were estimated from the blood samples, however, only some were liver-specific and directly associated with hepatobiliary health status, while others could also indicate health status of other tissue, i.e., heart, kidney, etc.

The primary outcomes will be defined as follow-up levels of ALAT, GGT, ALP, and total bilirubin.

Secondary liver-specific outcomes include follow-up levels of ASAT, ApoB, LDL-C, HDL-C, TC, and TG.

Secondary non-liver-specific outcomes include follow-up levels of FBG, HbA1c, CRP, sCr, and SHBG.

Covariates

Covariates were chosen a priori based on a review of the literature and directed acyclic graphs. Information on covariates includes information on aver-

age intakes of all other food groups retrieved from the Oxford WebQ (refined cereal, whole grain cereal, dairy products, dietary fats, fruits, vegetables, nuts, mixed dishes, potatoes and tubers, eggs, non-alcoholic beverages, alcoholic beverages, snacks, and sauces and condiments) and geographical region of recruitment (10 UK regions (29)). Other covariates were self-reported at the baseline visit and include information on sex, age, ethnicity, yearly income, educational level, Townsend Deprivation Index (0 indicates that an individual lives in an area with overall mean deprivation, positive values indicate higher material deprivation while negative values indicate relative affluence (31)), cohabitation, physical activity, smoking status, use of medication for cholesterol, hypertension, or diabetes, and family history of heart disease, stroke, hypertension, or diabetes. Usual alcohol consumption (g ethanol/day) was estimated as the average of the responses to the Oxford WebQs, while BMI was estimated based on weight and height measured by trained professionals at the baseline visit.

Sample size

For this cohort study, only participants with two or more 24 h dietary assessments and complete information on covariates who provided blood samples at baseline and at follow-up will be included in the analyses.

Sample size rationale

Variables

Measures variables

Exposures: g/week consumption of legumes, meats, poultry, and fish

Outcomes: alanine aminotransferase (ALAT), aspartate aminotransferase (ASAT), gamma glutamyltransferase (GGT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), apolipoprotein-B (ApoB), low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), total cholesterol (TC), serum triglycerides (TG), fasting blood glucose (FBG), glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), C-reactive protein (CRP), serum creatinine (sCr), sex-hormone binding glycoprotein (SHBG), and total bilirubin.

Covariates: g/week consumption of fruits, vegetables, cereal products, dairy products, egg products, nuts, mixed dishes, condiments, added sugar and sweets, non-alcoholic beverages, and alcoholic beverages. Sex, age, ethnic group, Townsend depriva-

tion score, educational level, geographical region of recruitment (ten UK regions), cohabitation, BMI, physical activity, smoking status, use of medication for cholesterol, hypertension, or diabetes, family history of heart disease, stroke, hypertension, or diabetes.

Analysis plan

Statistical models

Standard summary statistics will be performed to describe the distribution of baseline characteristics and food consumption across different categories of legume consumption. Multivariable linear regression analyses will be used to estimate follow-up biomarker levels based on substituting equal masses of red and processed meat, poultry, or fish with legumes.

- Replacing red and processed meats, poultry, or fish with legumes (e.g., per 80 g/week)

Model 1 will be adjusted for sex (male, female), geographical region of recruitment (10 UK regions), age at recruitment (continuous), the baseline biomarker level of the outcome biomarker (continuous), and intakes of all other food groups apart from the food being replaced (refined cereal, whole grain cereal, dairy products, dietary fats, fruits, vegetables, nuts, mixed dishes, potatoes and tubers, eggs, non-alcoholic beverages, alcoholic beverages, snacks, and sauces and condiments). All food items will be accounted for based on their weight and analyses will be adjusted for the total amount of food consumed in g/week

Model 2 will further adjust for educational level (categorical; low [Certificate of Secondary Education (CSE), National Vocational Qualifications, Higher National Diploma, Higher National Certificates, other professional qualifications, or equivalent], intermediate [A levels, O levels, General Certificate of Secondary Education, or equivalent], high [College or University degree]), yearly income (categorical; <18,000£, 18,000-30,999£, 31,000-51,999£, 52,000-100,000£, >100,000£, prefer not to answer), Townsend Deprivation Index (continuous), cohabitation (categorical; alone, with spouse or partner, with non-partner, prefer not to answer), ethnicity (categorical; White, other), physical activity (categorical; low [0-9.9 METs/week], moderate [10-49.9 METs/week], and high [\geq 50 METs/week], unknown), alcohol consumption (continuous; g ethanol/week as restricted cubic splines with

4 knots), smoking status (continuous; average number of pack-years smoked between the age of 16 and age at recruitment), use of medication for cholesterol, blood pressure, or diabetes (yes/no), and family history of heart disease, stroke, hypertension, or diabetes (yes/no).

Model 3 will be further adjusted for BMI (continuous) as this may either confound or mediate the association between replacing red and processed meat, poultry, or fish with legumes and the liver-related blood biomarker levels at follow-up.

The linearity assumption for the substitution models will be evaluated using splines at the 10th, 50th, and 90th percentile of the exposures (legumes, red and processed meat, poultry, fish) and the associated biomarker outcome levels as proposed in: <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0007114523002040>. The spline fitted model will be compared with the model using exposures as linear predictors with likelihood ratio tests.

Secondary and sensitivity analyses

All secondary outcomes will be estimated in secondary analyses using similar substitution models as above.

Furthermore, secondary analyses will be conducted for the primary outcomes but in a study sample restricted to consumers of legumes.

Sensitivity analyses will include: i) Inclusion of fresh peas in the estimated weekly legume consumption. ii) Exclusion of soy milk from the estimated weekly legume consumption, as soy milk is unlikely to culinarily replace red and processed meat, poultry, or fish. All secondary and sensitivity analyses will follow the adjustment level in model 2 from the main analysis (i.e. all covariates included except BMI). All analyses will be conducted in R with a two-sided significance level of 5%.

Transformations

If biomarker concentrations are not normally distributed they will be log-transformed for analyses and back-transformed for interpretation.

Inference criteria

All analyses will be evaluated based on two-sided p-values. Values below 5% are classified as statistically significant. Inference on relevance and significance and the evaluation of, whether a result is meaningful will be based on the size of the estimate, and confidence intervals containing 0.

Missing data

Missing information will result in exclusion of participants apart from physical activity. This variable is made as a composite variable of participants' reported low, moderate, and high physical activity together with hours/day of any activity. No available information in any of these variables resulted in exclusion, while missing information in a single activity would result in physical activity being coded as unknown.

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